

EMPOWERING ENGLISH LEARNERS THROUGH TRANSLATING DIVERSE YOUNG ADULT FICTION VOICES

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The study aims to promote English language learning through the translation of diverse young adult (YA) fiction texts, thereby encouraging linguistic and cultural competence. Using a qualitative methodology, 30 intermediate English learners translated extracts from multicultural YA novels (e.g. *The Hate U Give*). Data were collected through translation tasks and reflective surveys and analyzed using a thematic coding methodology. The results show that vocabulary, cultural awareness and engagement were improved. Integrating short translation activities into YA literature helps to create an inclusive and interactive learning environment, in line with the principles of communicative language teaching. Interventions with digital translation tools can enhance accessibility and merit further investigation.